

A NEW FORMULA FOR CHAKSINE, THE ALKALOID OF *CASSIA ABSUS* AND SOME EXPERIMENTS ON ITS CONSTITUTION.

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The formula of chaksine, the alkaloid from *Cassia absus*, has been found to be $C_{11}H_{21}O_3N_3$ and not $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N_3$ as suggested by Siddiqui and Ahmed.

Siddiqui and Ahmed (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, **2A**, 421) have isolated two quaternary bases from the seeds of *Cassia absus*. The base chaksine has been given the formula $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N_3$ and its salts have been formulated as $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3Hal$. These authors isolated the iodide for which they found I, 39.4%, whilst their formula $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3I$ required I, 36.4%. Apart from this, they relied on the analysis of chaksine bicarbonate which was supposed to have the composition $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3.HCO_3, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$. It was dehydrated by heating at 100° and the anhydrous substance analysed. There is grave objection to accept the loss in *vacuo* at 100° to be due to the loss of $\frac{1}{2} H_2O$. It is quite well known that the bicarbonates of organic bases, like those of an alkali metal, lose carbon dioxide on heating as indeed has been found to be the case by us.

It appeared to the present authors that the formula of chaksine has not been satisfactorily determined. Chaksine iodide was prepared essentially by the method of Siddiqui and Ahmed (*loc. cit.*) but the substance had m.p. 180° with previous shrinkage (Siddiqui and Ahmed give m.p. 168°). We have also prepared the sulphate, nitrate, chloride and the bromide in a high state of purity and analysed these carefully. The results do not confirm the formula $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3X$. For example the iodide gives C, 37.2, 37.1; H, 6.1, 6.3; N, 11.9, 11.7; I, 34.9 (Siddiqui and Ahmed's data), whilst $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3I$ requires C, 41.2; H, 5.7; I, 36.4%, whereas $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3I$ requires C, 37.37; H, 5.7; N, 11.9; I, 35.9%. Siddiqui and Ahmed did not record any C and H values for the iodide.

Siddiqui and Ahmed have described the platinichloride of the chloride and from their data the M.W. for the chloride comes out as 261.5. The chloride itself has been prepared by us and analysed. It gives C, 50.57; H, 8.1; N, 15.5, 15.66. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3Cl$ requires C, 50.48; H, 7.7; N, 16.0; M.W. 261.5, whilst $C_{12}H_{20}ON_3Cl$ requires C, 55.9; H, 7.7

N, 16.3%. Therefore it would appear that chaksine is $C_{11}H_{21}O_3N_3$, ($C_{11}H_{23}O_3N_3$ is also possible from the analytical data but less probable) and not $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N_3$ as suggested by Siddiqui and Ahmed. In the experimental sequel, we have described the preparation and analyses of a large number of salts which mitigate clearly against C_{12} -formula for chaksine.

The nitrate of chaksine gives with strong sulphuric acid a substance which we have designated as nitrochaksine sulphate formed by the loss of a molecule of water reminiscent of urea nitrate-nitrourea or guanidine nitrate—nitroguanidine change. With sodium hydroxide and barium hydroxide ammonia is copiously liberated from chaksine but unfortunately the product of the action of alkali has not yet been isolated in a state of purity. With hydrogen peroxide and trace of ferrous sulphate, chaksine sulphate gives formaldehyde recognised by the dimedon condensation product. With potassium permanganate, chaksine sulphate gives oxalic acid and a mixture of dibasic acids which have been separated by esterification and fractionation, of these esters one analysed as $C_{10}H_{18}O_4$, and another as $C_7H_{14}O_3$.

Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the extraction of chaksine from the seeds, ethyl alcohol was substituted for methyl alcohol prescribed by Siddiqui and Ahmed. The brownish yellow syrupy residue, after the removal of solvent at 40° from the neutralised and acidified extract, was freed of oily matter by repeated extraction with ether.

The *iodide*, isolated essentially as described by Siddiqui and Ahmed, was repeatedly crystallised from hot water, m.p. 180° (after drying in high *vacuo* at 100°). [Found: C, 37.1, 37.2; H, 6.3, 6.1; N, 11.9, 11.9, 11.7; (Siddiqui and Ahmed gave I, 34.9). Calc. for $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3I$: C, 37.3; H, 5.7; N, 11.9; I, 35.9 per cent].

Chaksine sulphate, prepared from chaksine iodide or as described by Siddiqui and Ahmed, was repeatedly crystallised from water or dilute alcohol, m.p. 317° (decomp.). [Found after drying in high *vacuo* at 140° : C, 48.0; H, 7.7; N, 15.0, 14.96; S, 5.55. ($C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3$)₂SO₄ requires C, 48.18; H, 7.3; N, 15.3; S, 5.84 per cent. Siddiqui and Ahmed gave S, 5.85%. They do not give any other values. ($C_{12}H_{20}ON_3$)₂SO₄ requires C, 53.3; H, 7.4; N, 15.5; S, 5.93 per cent].

Chaksine Chloride.—To a hot suspension of chaksine sulphate in water (1 g. in 20 c.c.) was added powdered barium chloride (4 g.). After boiling

for 2 minutes, the solution was filtered and the filtrate saturated with sodium chloride. The crystalline precipitate was collected after cooling and then recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetone, m. p. 178° (after drying in *vacuo* at 100°), yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 50.57; H, 8.1; N, 15.66, 15.5, 15.7. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3Cl$ requires C, 50.48; H, 7.7; N, 16.0 per cent).

Chaksine bromide was prepared similarly with barium bromide in theoretical yield. It was crystallised successively from water and a mixture of alcohol and acetone, m.p. 186° (after drying in *vacuo* at 100°). (Found: C, 43.3; H, 6.8; N, 13.34, 13.26. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3Br$ requires C, 43.2; H, 6.5; N, 13.7 per cent). The C_{12} formula requires C, 47.6 per cent.

Chaksine Nitrate.—Chaksine iodide (2 g.), dissolved in water (20 c.c.), was decomposed with silver nitrate solution (1.2 g. in 10 c.c. of water) or potassium nitrate solution by warming on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. After filtration, the nitrate crystallised on cooling. It was recrystallised in transparent rectangular plates from hot water and then from alcohol. The substance after dehydration in *vacuo* lost its transparency and had m. p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: C, 45.8, 45.85; H, 6.91, 7.2; N, 19.3, 19.2, 19.5. $C_{11}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires C, 45.8; H, 6.9; N, 19.44 per cent).

Nitrochaksine Sulphate.—To ice-cold sulphuric acid (2.5 c.c.) was added chaksine nitrate (0.9 g.) in small quantities at a time. The mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ minute and then poured to ice. The precipitate was crystallised from hot dilute alcohol, m. p. 176° (decomp.). This substance partially decomposes on drying in *vacuo* at 140° . (Found after drying at 110° : C, 39.8; H, 6.5; N, 16.4, 16.5 per cent). The nature of this substance is being investigated.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Chaksine Chloride.—To an ice-cold solution of chaksine chloride (1 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was added a solution of sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and the mixture acidified with hydrochloric acid. A substance separated out almost immediately. The mixture was heated to boiling to dissolve the precipitate and then was allowed to cool. The colourless substance now separating was collected and crystallised from water and then from alcohol. During the action no evolution of nitrogen was noticed. The substance (transparent plates) had m. p. 221° (decomp.). (Found: C, 45.7, 46.01; H, 7.04, 7.06; N, 18.8, 18.78 per cent).

Oxidation of Chaksine Sulphate with Hydrogen Peroxide.—To a solution of chaksine sulphate (3 g.) in water (250 c.c.) warmed to 80° were added a few drops of ferrous sulphate solution. When the temperature of the

mixture was 58° , hydrogen peroxide (15 c.c.) was added gradually avoiding further rise in temperature. The mixture was distilled and the distillate bubbled through an alcoholic solution of dimethyldihydroresorcin. After acidification of the dimedon solution with acetic acid, it was refluxed for 3 hours. The precipitate was treated with benzene and then reprecipitated with petrol ether. After rejecting the first precipitate, the solution on concentration gave needles which after crystallisation from hot petroleum ether had m. p. 188° and was identified as the formaldehyde condensation product. There is evidence of other substances being formed and these are under investigation.

Oxidation of Chaksine Sulphate with Potassium Permanganate in Alkaline Medium.—A solution of sodium hydroxide (2.5 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was added gradually under cooling to a solution of chaksine sulphate (7 g.) in water (300 c.c.). To this solution was then added gradually and with thorough shaking, during 1 hour, potassium permanganate solution (200 c.c., 5%) and the temperature during addition was maintained at 30° . The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hours and then filtered, the precipitate being washed several times with hot water. The filtrate and the washings were mixed together and concentrated in *vacuo*, and the distillate was trapped in hydrochloric acid, whence ammonium chloride was isolated and identified.

The concentrated mother-liquor was strongly acidified with concentrated sulphuric acid and then extracted repeatedly with ether. The ethereal extract after dehydration over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removal of the solvent, gave a liquid which was acidic in reaction. The acidic liquid was esterified and fractionated. From the first fraction oxalic acid was isolated after hydrolysis and identified (mixed m. p. $98-99^{\circ}$). The second fraction, b.p. $80^{\circ}/3$ mm., analysed as follows: (Found: C, 60.02; H, 9.49. $C_{10}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 59.4; H, 8.9 per cent). The third ester, b.p. $100-105^{\circ}/3$ mm., gave C, 57.35; H, 8.9. $C_4H_9OOCOC_2H_5$ requires C, 57.5; H, 9.5 per cent.